

Titrimetric Determination of Antimony(V) with Iron(II)

L. S. A. DIKSHITULU* and K. VIJAYA RAJU

Department of Chemistry, Andhra University, Waltair.

Manuscript received 21 May 1977, revised 2 November 1977, accepted 1 February 1978

A direct titrimetric method has been developed for the determination of antimony(V) using iron(II) as a reductimetric reagent in a strong phosphoric acid medium. The phosphoric acid concentration should be at least 11M (70% V/V) and hydrochloric acid concentration 2M for a satisfactory titration. The end point can be determined either potentiometrically or using thionine as indicator. Sulphate, perchlorate and acetate ions do not interfere in this method; arsenic(V), copper(II), selenium(IV), selenium(VI) and tellurium(VI) interfere. Tellurium(IV) does not interfere upto an overall concentration of 0.004M. The formal redox potentials of the Sb(V)/Sb(III) couple in media of varying phosphoric acid concentration have been determined for the first time.

EARLIER methods¹⁻⁴ for the determination of antimony(V) consist in treating antimony(V) with excess of KI in acid medium and titrating the liberated iodine with hypo. In these methods a coloured compound of the formula $SbCl_5 \cdot 3KI \cdot 5H_2O$ which is sometimes formed was stated to seriously interfere with the titration. In a few other methods antimony(V) is reduced in acid solution either with KI⁵ or with iodine solution and red phosphorous⁶, the liberated iodine boiled off with excess of carbon dioxide and the antimony(III) formed titrated with standard iodine solution. McCay⁷ determined antimony(V) by shaking 3-4N HCl solutions in a mercury reductor in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide for one hour and titrating the antimony(III) formed with $KBrO_3$ using methyl orange as indicator. Schreider⁸ accomplished the reduction of antimony(V) with SO_2 and the antimony(III) formed was determined by the bromate method after boiling off the excess SO_2 . Tananaev and Davitashvili⁹ determined antimony(V) by treating it with tin and HCl and titrating the tin(II) formed in the reaction with $KMnO_4$. In the more recent methods the determination of antimony(V) is carried out potentiometrically by titrating with tin(II)¹⁰, vanadium(III)¹¹, chromium(II), vanadium(II), titanium(III), and thiourea¹².

Eventhough a large number of methods are available for the titrimetric determination of antimony(V), no method is entirely satisfactory, because the visual end point methods are tedious while the potentiometric ones need an inert atmosphere, high temperatures and special apparatus for the storage of the reductant solutions. We have now developed a titrimetric method for the determination of antimony(V) using iron(II) as a reductimetric reagent in a strong phosphoric acid medium, which does not suffer from the disadvantages mentioned above. The end point can be determined at room temperature either potentiometrically or using thionine as indicator.

Experimental

Solutions: An approximately 0.025M solution of antimony(V) was prepared by dissolving about 3 gms. of sodium pyroantimonate (BDH, LR) in 250 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid and making it upto 500 ml. Its strength was determined employing the method of McCay⁷.

Approximately 0.025M solution of antimony(III) was prepared by dissolving about 0.36 gms of antimonous oxide (May & Baker, LR) in 50 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid and making it upto 100 ml. Its strength was determined with potassium bromate using methyl red as indicator.

Approximately 0.05M solution of iron(II) was prepared from ferrous ammonium sulphate (BDH, Analar) and standardised in the usual way.

A 0.1% solution of thionine was prepared in water. Basynt, A. R., phosphoric and hydrochloric acids were used in this investigation. The strengths of these acids were determined with standard solutions of sodium hydroxide using "Elico" p^H meter Model 10.

Apparatus: OSAW potentiometer and suspension galvanometer were used. A bright platinum electrode (0.2 mm diameter) was used as the indicator electrode and a saturated calomel electrode as the reference electrode. An agar-agar salt bridge containing 30% of potassium chloride was used.

Procedure: To an aliquot volume (upto 10 ml) of antimony(V) solution taken in a 150 ml beaker, 70 ml of phosphoric acid and enough hydrochloric acid to give an overall concentration of 2M were added. The solution was titrated with iron(II) solution while it was being stirred by means of a magnetic stirrer. The

potentials were measured 30 seconds after the addition of each instalment of the titrant till 75% of the titration was completed. There afterwards stable potentials were obtained only after waiting for two minutes after the addition of the titrant. However, at the end point one has to wait for four minutes for the stable potentials to be established. After the equivalence point the potentials get stabilised immediately after the addition of iron(II). The break in potential at the end point corresponds to about 60mV/0.04 ml of 0.05M iron(II).

The titration can also be carried out using a visual indicator. The conditions for the visual titration were the same as for the potentiometric one except that three drops of thionine should be added and a carbon dioxide atmosphere maintained to prevent aerial oxidation of the leuco base of the dye. The colour change at the end point is from green to pale yellow.

Results and Discussion

Some of the representative results obtained using the procedures described above are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—TITRIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF ANTIMONY(V) WITH IRON(II)

Potentiometric method Antimony(V), mg.		Visual end-point method Antimony(V), mg.	
Taken	Found	Taken	Found
9.14	9.17	7.56	7.53
13.98	14.02	10.47	10.50
15.50	15.45	13.31	13.37
20.28	20.20	15.50	15.45
23.72	23.67	18.88	18.94
29.05	29.02	29.90	29.90

The accuracy of the potentiometric method was $\pm 0.4\%$ and that of the visual indicator method was $\pm 0.5\%$. The precision in both the methods was determined by titrating ten samples each containing 15.50 mg of antimony(V). The averages and standard deviations were 15.502 mg and 0.04 mg in the potentiometric method and 15.504 mg and 0.05 mg in the visual indicator method.

During the reduction of antimony(V) with iron(II) in phosphoric acid medium it was noticed that the reduction proceeds quantitatively to antimony(III) provided the medium contains at least 1M (or 70% by volume) phosphoric acid and 2M hydrochloric acid. In order to explain the conditions necessary for the quantitative reduction of antimony(V), a knowledge of the formal redox potentials of Sb(V)/Sb(III) couple and Fe(III)/Fe(II) couple in media of varying phosphoric acid concentration is necessary. The data on the redox potentials of the Fe(III)/Fe(II) couple in varying phos-

phoric acid concentrations were available from the work of Gopala Rao and Sagi¹³. However, the formal redox potentials of Sb(V)/Sb(III) couple in media of varying phosphoric acid concentrations were not available from the literature. We have, therefore, determined the formal redox potentials of Sb(V)/Sb(III) couple in media of varying phosphoric acid concentrations, adopting a method essentially similar to that described by Gopala Rao and Dikshitulu¹⁴ for the determination of the formal redox potentials of V(IV)/V(III) couple in phosphoric acid medium. The potentials were determined at 30° keeping the total [antimony] at 0.0025M and the total dilution at 100 ml. In addition to phosphoric acid the solutions contain 0.5M hydrochloric acid. The potential data thus obtained are tabulated in Table 2.

TABLE 2—FORMAL REDOX POTENTIALS OF Sb(V)/Sb(III) COUPLE IN MEDIA OF VARYING PHOSPHORIC ACID CONCENTRATIONS

Concentration of Phosphoric acid, M	Formal redox potential (N.H.E.), V
3.0	0.872
4.0	0.848
6.0	0.808
8.0	0.776
10.0	0.752
12.0	0.744
14.0	0.740

These potentials are reproducible within ± 5 mV. The potential data incorporated in Table 2 along with that of the Fe(III)/Fe(II) couple is shown graphically in Fig. 1. The potential data could not be determined accurately below 3M phosphoric acid concentration because of the hydrolysis of antimony solutions.

Fig. 1. Formal Redox Potential of Sb(V)/Sb(III) (○—○) and Fe(III)/Fe(II) (△—△) couples in a medium of varying phosphoric acid concentration.

From Fig. 1. it may be seen that the potentials of both Sb(V)/Sb(III) and Fe(III)/Fe(II) couples decrease with increasing phosphoric acid concentration. However, it appears surprising that even though the potential difference between the two couples at various phosphoric acid concentrations is nearly equal, the reduction proceeds quantitatively only at a phosphoric acid concentration of 11M or above. Thus the potentials data does not seem to be helpful in explaining the conditions needed for the quantitative reduction of antimony(V) to antimony(III).

For a rapid and quantitative reduction of antimony(V) to antimony(III), in addition to a minimum concentration of about 11M phosphoric acid, a chloride ion concentration of 2M was found to be necessary. The authors feel that chloride ion facilitates the electron transfer from iron(II) to antimony(V) probably through the formation of a bridged complex. Bromide ion was found to catalyse the reaction better than the chloride ion, thus strengthening our contention that these ions facilitate the reaction through the formation of a halide bridge. However, even bromide ion should be present at a concentration of more than 1M for the titration to be satisfactory. Since it is difficult to provide such a high concentration of bromide ion (excepting through the use of hydrobromic acid which is not a common reagent in the laboratory) we preferred the use of chloride ion in the titration.

Interferences

Among the anions sulphate, perchlorate and acetate ions do not interfere; arsenic(V) interferes by slowly getting reduced to arsenic(III). Among the cations, copper(II), selenium(IV), selenium(VI) and tellurium(VI) interfere. Tellurium(IV) does not interfere upto an overall concentration of 0.004M.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the University Grants Commission for financial assistance.

References

1. A. TRAVERS and JOUOT, *Compt. rend.*, 1927, 184, 635; *Chem. Abs.*, 1927, 21, 1606⁴.
2. JACQUES PENS, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1938, 47, 129; *Chem. Abs.*, 1938, 32, 4098⁹.
3. N. D. BIRYUKOV, *Zavodsk. Lab.*, 1962, 28, 671; *Chem. Abs.*, 1963, 58, 2831g.
4. L. SZEBELLEDY, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1930, 81, 36; *Chem. Abs.*, 1930, 24, 4478³.
5. P. ED. WINKLER, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1927, 36, 491; *Chem. Abs.*, 1928, 22, 40⁹.
6. E. A. JOHNSON and E. J. NEWMAN, *Analyst.*, 1955, 80, 631.
7. L. W. McCAY, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1933, 5, 1.
8. R. I. SHREIDER, *Khim. Farm. Prom.*, 1933, 151-2; *Chem. Abs.*, 1934, 28, 429¹.
9. I. TANANAEV and E. G. DAVITASHVILI, *Zavodskaya Lab.*, 1937, 6, 1382; *Cf. C. A.*, 31, 968⁹; *Chem. Abs.*, 1938, 32, 2451⁹.
10. K. DAUKSAS and L. NARUSKEVICIUS, *Mokslo Darbai.*, 1957, 16, 161; *Chem. Abs.*, 1961, 55, 2355h.
11. L. NARUSKEVICIUS and K. DAUKSAS, *Chem. ir. chem. Tech.*, 1961, 1, 11; *Chem. Abs.*, 1963, 58, 5027a.
12. L. NARUSKEVICIUS, *hietuvos TSR Auksluju Mokyklu Mokslo Darbai. Chem. ir. Chem. Technol.*, 1965, 7, 149; *Chem. Abs.*, 1966, 64, 14943h.
13. G. GOPALARAO and S. R. SAGI, *Talanta.*, 1962, 9, 715.
14. G. GOPALARAO and L. S. A. DIKSHITULU, *Talanta.*, 1963, 10, 295.